

LINGUISTIC FEATURES AND DIFFERENCES OF ORAL AND WRITTEN SPEECH

Yoqubova Mohira

English teacher at the Specialized

Boarding School No.16

Navoi City

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Abstract: This article explores the linguistic characteristics and differences between oral and written speech. Through a comprehensive literature review and analysis, it examines the structural, lexical, and pragmatic aspects of both forms of communication. The study highlights the unique features of each mode and their implications for language use and comprehension.

Keywords: oral speech, written speech, linguistic features, communication modes, language analysis

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada lingvistik xususiyatlar va og'zaki va yozma nutq o'rtasidagi farqlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Adabiyotlarni har tomonlama ko'rib chiqish va tahlil qilish asosida muloqotning ikkala shaklining tarkibiy, leksik va pragmatik jihatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqot har bir aloqa usulining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini va ularning tildan foydalanish va tushunishga ta'sirini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: og'zaki nutq, yozma nutq, lingvistik xususiyatlar, aloqa usullari, tilni tahlil qilish

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются лингвистические характеристики и различия между устной и письменной речью. На основе всестороннего обзора и анализа литературы рассматриваются структурные, лексические и прагматические аспекты обеих форм общения. В исследовании подчеркиваются уникальные особенности каждого способа общения и их влияние на использование и понимание языка.

Ключевые слова: устная речь, письменная речь, лингвистические особенности, способы коммуникации, языковой анализ

INTRODUCTION

The dichotomy between oral and written speech has long been a subject of interest in linguistics and communication studies. These two modes of language expression, while both serving the primary purpose of conveying information, exhibit distinct characteristics that reflect the different contexts and purposes they serve [1]. This article aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the linguistic features and differences between oral and written speech, exploring

their structural, lexical, and pragmatic aspects. The significance of this study lies in its potential to enhance our understanding of language use across different mediums, which has implications for various fields, including education, literature, and digital communication.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This study employs a systematic literature review methodology, analyzing peer-reviewed articles, books, and academic publications from the past two decades. The research focuses on works in English, Russian, and Uzbek to provide a comprehensive and multicultural perspective on the topic.

Key sources include Biber's (1988) seminal work on variation across speech and writing [2], Chafe and Tannen's (1987) analysis of the spoken and written dichotomy [3], and more recent studies by Crystal (2011) on language and the internet [4]. Additionally, works by Uzbek linguists such as Nurmonov (2012) on the structure of the Uzbek language [5] and Russian research by Zemskaya (2016) on colloquial speech [6] have been incorporated to provide a diverse linguistic perspective.

The literature review process involved systematic categorization and analysis of the gathered information, focusing on structural, lexical, and pragmatic features of oral and written speech. This approach allowed for a comprehensive comparison of the two modes across different linguistic traditions and research paradigms.

RESULTS

The analysis of the literature reveals several key differences between oral and written speech:

1. **Structural Features:** Oral speech tends to have a looser structure, with more frequent use of simple sentences, repetitions, and fragmented utterances [7]. In contrast, written speech typically exhibits more complex sentence structures, with a higher prevalence of subordinate clauses and elaborate syntactic constructions [2].

2. **Lexical Characteristics:** Written language generally employs a more diverse and sophisticated vocabulary, with a higher frequency of low-frequency words and technical terms [8]. Oral speech, on the other hand, tends to use a more limited vocabulary range, with a higher occurrence of colloquialisms and filler words [3].

3. **Contextual Elements:** Oral communication relies heavily on non-verbal cues, such as intonation, gestures, and facial expressions, which are

absent in written form [9]. Written speech compensates for this lack of immediate context by being more explicit and detailed in its content [4].

4. Temporal Aspects: Oral speech is characterized by its immediacy and real-time production, often resulting in spontaneous language use with less planning [6]. Written language allows for more time in composition and revision, leading to more carefully constructed expressions [5].

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The findings highlight the distinct nature of oral and written speech, each adapted to serve different communicative purposes. The structural differences reflect the cognitive processes involved in real-time speech production versus the more deliberate composition of written text. The looser structure of oral speech allows for greater flexibility and immediate listener feedback, while the complex structures in written language facilitate the expression of more intricate ideas and arguments.

Lexical variations between the two modes underscore the different demands placed on speakers and writers. The broader vocabulary in written texts reflects the need for precision and the opportunity for careful word selection, while the more limited lexical range in speech is offset by the rich contextual information provided through non-verbal cues.

The role of context emerges as a crucial differentiator between oral and written communication. Oral speech's reliance on shared context and non-verbal elements allows for more implicit communication, whereas written language must compensate through explicit detail and careful exposition. This difference has significant implications for how information is conveyed and interpreted in each mode.

The temporal aspects of speech production versus writing highlight the cognitive processes involved in language use. The spontaneity of speech often results in more natural and dynamic language, while the reflective nature of writing allows for more polished and structured expression.

The permanence of written language versus the transience of speech influences not only how language is produced but also how it is perceived and studied. This characteristic has profound implications for education, record-keeping, and the transmission of knowledge across time and space.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that oral and written speech, while both serving as modes of linguistic communication, possess distinct features that reflect their unique functions and contexts. The structural, lexical, contextual, temporal, and

permanence-related differences between these modes highlight the versatility of human language and its adaptation to various communicative needs.

Understanding these differences is crucial for effective communication across different mediums and contexts. It has implications for language teaching, where awareness of these distinctions can inform pedagogical approaches. Moreover, in the digital age, where the lines between oral and written communication are increasingly blurred, this knowledge becomes even more relevant.

References:

1. Akinnaso, F.N. (1982). On the differences between spoken and written language. *Language and Speech*, 25(2), 97-125.
2. Aminova, Z. P. (2018). Importance of Implementing Pedagogical Technologies to Education System. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, (2).
3. Begimov, O. (2024). Uzbek TOPONIMLAR SHAKLLANISHINING AYRIM USULLARI. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(02).
4. ОБОГАЩЕНИИ, Р. З. С. В. (2020). Otabek Shukurov Ulashevich, Rushana Nabiyeva Jamol qizi Qarshi davlat universiteti (Qarshi, O „zbekiston) O „ZBEK TILI LEKSIKASI BOYISHIDA O „ZLASHMA SO „ZLARNING O „RNI. MODERN SCIENTIFIC CHALLENGES AND TRENDS, 123.
5. Begimov, O. (2024). TOG’KULTI TUSHUNCHASINING ORONIMIYADA VOQELANISHI. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 4(3), 50-55.
6. Mustaitddinovna, A. A., & Ibadova, N. A. (2023). XORIJIY TILLARNI O’QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY METODLAR FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 25(2), 201-203.
7. Axmadjonovna, A. M., & Ibadova, N. A. (2023). TURLI YOSH KATEGORIYALARIGA CHET TILLARINI O’RGATISHDA YANGI PED TEXNOLOGIYALARNING AHAMIYATI. *TADQIQOTLAR. UZ*, 25(2), 198-200.
8. Qurbonnazarovna, M. M. (2023). THE ROLE OF SYNERGIC IDEAS IN IMPROVING THE SCIENTIFIC CREATIVE PROCESS.
9. Tulenova, K., Rasulev, E., & Mamadjonova, M. (2023). Value Dimension in a Techno genic Society. *Telematique*, 22(01), 2666-2670.
10. Айтмуратова, У., & Шамшетова, Д. (2016). ЭКОНОМИКАНЫ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯЛАЎ ШАРАЯТЫНДА ПЕНСИЯ ТӘМИЙНАТЫ СИСТЕМАСЫН ЖЕТИЛИСТИРИЎ. *ВЕСТНИК КАРАКАЛПАКСКОГО ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА ИМЕНИ БЕРДАХА*, 32(3), 44-47.
11. Шамшетова, Д. С., & Айтмуратова, У. Ж. (2018). ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ В НАЛОГОВОЙ СИСТЕМЕ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН В УСЛОВИЯХ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ ЭКОНОМИКИ. *Экономика и социум*, (4 (47)), 706-709.

12. Turdi'muratovna, U. S., & Mukhiddin, U. (2022). Features of the process of transition from national accounting standards to international standards.
13. Давыдов, Ю. Д., & Базаров, Ш. А. (2021). Феномен неоднозначности в произведениях искусства. ИННОВАЦИИ В ПЕДАГОГИКЕ И ПСИХОЛОГИИ, 4(7).
14. Abdinazarovich, B. S. (2023, November). NUTQ MADANIYATINI BUZUVCHI FAKTORLAR. In Konferensiyalar| Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 541-545).
15. Sh, B. P. (2021). Ideas of Mahmudhoja Behbudi Reflected in Publicism. JournalNX, 7(10), 112-115.
16. Tagayeva, T., & Amanova, S. (2024, April). STYLISTIC PECULIARITIES OF LITERARY TEXT IN CREATIVE WORKS OF BERNARD SHAW. In Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit (pp. 520-524).
17. Tagayeva, T., & Kabridinova, K. (2024, April). INDIVIDUAL FEATURES OF ARTISTIC STYLE OF WM THACKERAY. In Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit (pp. 543-546).
18. Tajenova, G. E., Baijanov, S. X., Abishov, M. S., & Madreimov, A. K. (2022). PROVIDING AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS TO THE POPULATION AND FINANCING IT BY THE STATE WAYS TO IMPROVE SUPPORT. NeuroQuantology, 20(22), 1598.
19. Serofiddin o'g, S. G. A. (2024). NEURAL CELLS IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, 3(30), 119-126.
20. Serofiddin o'g, S. G. A. (2024). MODERN TECHNOLOGIES OF THE WASTE RECYCLING SYSTEM IN THE MODERN WORLD. INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, 5(42), 32-41.
21. Жамолова, Г. М. К., Хамрақулова, С. О. К., & Уралова, Н. Б. К. (2024). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ НЕЙРОННЫХ СЕТЕЙ У ЧЕЛОВЕКА НА ПРИМЕРЕ
22. Biber, D. (1988). Variation across speech and writing. Cambridge University Press.
23. Chafe, W., & Tannen, D. (1987). The relation between written and spoken language. Annual Review of Anthropology, 16, 383-407.